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Street-level surface and air temperatures in the Urban Center of Málaga, Spain

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ABSTRACT

Increasing urbanization is leading to rising temperatures in cities, especially in their central areas, where artificial covers, street canyons and human-induced heat release are more common. This urban microclimate is especially critical in historical centers, as the protection of these areas' cultural assets hinders the introduction of adaptation measures. In this context, this study developed a methodology to characterize the microclimate in historical city centers, using the Mediterranean city of Málaga in southern Spain as a paradigmatic case study. To this end, field measurements were carried out by using a bicycle mobile station and a handheld thermal imaging camera along the so-called Picassian route, covering eleven different streets and eight historical buildings (eleven façades) where air and surface temperatures were collected. The results showed significant differences in the values of air and surface temperatures, so studies of urban microclimate should consider both types of temperatures together, and especially the temperature of building façades, which is often ignored due to the lack of open data about it but has notable different patterns. An analysis of the relationship between field data and a range of spatial factors related to the morphology and surface artificiality of urban areas revealed that shading and tree planting might provide a solution to heat mitigation. For historical centers with important space constraints, these solutions may consist of installing awnings and green façades.

1. Introduction

Climate change is one of the greatest global challenges of the 21st century, with the potential to impact the social, environmental, and economic dimensions of cities (UN-Habitat, 2022). Although cities cover only 2 % of the Earth's surface, they play a significant role in climate change contributing to global energy consumption and carbon dioxide emissions (Fang et al., 2015). Currently, more than half of the world's population lives in urban areas, a figure projected to surpass 65 % by 2050 (Martin et al., 2022). This urbanization intensifies the risk of rising urban temperatures, which are increasingly recognized as a major threat (Kumar, 2021; UN-Habitat, 2022). According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), the combination of global warming and population growth in already warm urban centers is the main driver of increased urban heat exposure (IPCC, 2023). In this context, urban

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planning authorities must focus on adaptation strategies to deal with rising temperatures (Bonilla-Bedoya et al., 2022; Fan and Wei, 2022; Lin et al., 2021).

Climate change impacts are exacerbated in urban areas through the so-called ‘urban heat island’ (UHI) effect, a climatic phenomenon that creates warmer and drier conditions in urban areas (urban microclimate) compared to their surrounding rural areas (Oke, 1982). Urban microclimate is primarily caused by the geometry and materials used in urban infrastructure, such as impervious surfaces like asphalt and concrete (Rizwan et al., 2008). The UHI effect is being studied in various cities around the world using experimental data and/or computer simulation tools (Cheval et al., 2024) based on air or surface temperature, resulting in two types of UHI: Canopy UHI (CUHI) and Surface UHI (SUHI) (Gourfi et al., 2022). Data collection to model one or the other can come from satellite techniques, weather stations, remote sensors, and thermal images (Martin et al., 2022). There is no consensus on which method is best for studying the urban microclimate but the choice depends on the scale (city, neighborhood, building) and precision.

Air temperature records are limited to site-specific analyses due to the location of the stations, requiring the use of interpolation methods for 2D models. In recent years, the use of Land Surface Temperature (LST) records has gained importance due to the availability of satellite data (Mas’uddin et al., 2023; Zargari et al., 2024); however, this option is limited to large-scale studies due to the coarse granularity of the data. Both approaches differ in the data used in terms of collection (field vs. remote sensing) as well as spatial and temporal resolution. These discrepancies hinder the joint assessment of CUHI and SUHI.

As a bridge between the two options, the use of mobile data acquisition units, particularly in the form of bicycles, has also been examined. Although the first attempts to use this approach date back more than two decades (Melhuish and Pedder, 1998), it has gained considerable attention in recent years (Heusinkveld et al., 2014; Viejira et al., 2023; Yokoyama et al., 2018). These mobile stations are generally equipped with a GPS and a datalogger that enable the recording of time series georeferenced data of both air and surface temperature and relative humidity (Pena Acosta et al., 2023). The use of these units enables data collection campaigns to be carried out in urban areas, while their mobility and high-frequency measurement capacity allow the scale of analysis to be reduced to the micro level (e.g., streets), thus solving the shortcomings of the models built using data from weather stations or remote sensing.

A common limitation in previous studies measuring temperature data using mobile stations was the collection of only air temperature data (Cao et al., 2020; Dorigon and Amorim, 2019; Shi et al., 2018; Ziter et al., 2019); however, recent studies have built more complete mobile stations that can also record LST (Pena Acosta et al., 2023). Still, a gap remains, as previous approaches have largely overlooked detailed assessments of building façade temperatures a key factor considering the significant role that wall and roof envelope materials play in the formation of urban microclimate (Wonorahardjo et al., 2022). In response, this study coupled the use of a bicycle with a thermal camera to record both air temperature and the surface temperature of buildings and pavements.

Another related area of research addresses the relationship between UHI (either SUHI or CUHI) and characteristics such as building density and height, vegetation, albedo, or sky view factor (svf), for which regression and machine learning models have been built. Most of these use LST as a proxy for the SUHI effect (Addas, 2023; Furuya et al., 2023; Jato-Espino et al., 2022), although there are some cases where temperature data stemmed from mobile station records (Pena Acosta et al., 2023; Ziter et al., 2019). These studies tested the accuracy of such models and interpreted the relationships between the various parameters involved, but did not use this information to propose alternative scenarios for urban microclimate attenuation.

Moreover, the vast majority of prior investigations have been conducted in urban areas with humid subtropical (Yadav and Sharma, 2018; Yokoyama et al., 2018), temperate oceanic (Pigliatile and Pisello, 2018; Tsin et al., 2016), or temperate continental climate regimes (Rajkovich and Larsen, 2016; Ziter et al., 2019). Although there are studies under Mediterranean climate conditions (Romero

Fig. 1. Flowchart of the main steps constituting the proposed urban microclimate evaluation approach.

Rodríguez et al., 2023; Speak and Salbitano, 2022), field measurements were limited to air temperature. Therefore, a more comprehensive characterization of the phenomenon in Mediterranean urban areas is required, as these are especially sensitive to health-related temperature impacts, with Málaga (southern Spain) standing out as one of the ten European cities that record the most deaths in summer due to the UHI effect (Jungman et al., 2023).

Taking all this into account, this research aimed to evaluate the urban microclimate in the historical center of Málaga by collecting data on historical buildings, pavements, and air temperatures in summer. To achieve this goal, three research questions (RQs) were formulated to close the gaps identified in the previous literature:

1. RQ1: What are the relationships between air, building, and pavement temperatures?
2. RQ2: How sensitive are the trends in urban microclimate to the weather conditions of the study area?
3. RQ3: Can the collected field records be used to identify the main drivers of urban microclimate?

2. Methodology

The proposed approach consisted of three main steps, as depicted in Fig. 1. First, temperature data were collected using two different methods: a bicycle mobile station and a handheld thermal camera. Second, the collected data were processed, which involved arranging and classifying the data by street and building names, as well as calculating pavement albedo based on images. Third, the data were analyzed through descriptive statistics and correlation analyses to examine associations between raw temperatures, mean temperatures, spatial factors, and the comparison of low and high temperatures.

2.1. Study area

The city selected for the study is Málaga in Andalusia, southern Spain. Málaga has a population of 578,460 and covers an area of

Fig. 2. Location and delimitation of the data collection route in the historical center of Málaga, Spain.

395 km² (Román López et al., 2022). Located on a fluvial plain, Málaga is characterized by 2905 h of sunshine per year with a total annual rainfall ranging from 400 to 700 mm (Senciales-González et al., 2020). The Mediterranean Sea can act as a thermal regulator and additionally contribute to humidity (Román López et al., 2022). The annual average temperature ranges from 18.1 °C to 21.7 °C, depending on the meteorological station considered (Higueras et al., 2021). During the summer months (June to September), the city experiences high levels of solar radiation, insolation, and periods of overheating (Román López et al., 2022; Senciales-González et al., 2020). Overall, Málaga is categorized as mediterranean climate, but activities and urban structure also condition the local microclimate (Román López et al., 2022).

Tourism is one of the main economic drivers of the city of Málaga, particularly in the summer months (Diputación Provincial de Málaga et al., 2023). Among the city's urban tourism offerings, the 'Picassian Route' stands out as a popular path through the historical center of Málaga, allowing visitors to explore streets and historical buildings associated with the life of the painter Pablo Picasso (Área de Turismo del Ayuntamiento de Málaga, 2023). However, the historical center of Málaga, being a densely built area with limited exposure to marine breezes, experiences increased temperatures, higher UHI values, and a lower bioclimatic rating (Higueras et al., 2021; Senciales-González et al., 2020). These microclimatic conditions can significantly impact the comfort and overall experience of tourists, especially along routes like the Picasso Route during peak summer months. Given the potential influence of these urban climate factors on tourism, this study focused on a path within the Picasso Route. Fig. 2 depicts the location of the city of Málaga and the delineation of the proposed temperature data collection route, which was 1.5 km long and crossed eleven different streets and eight historical buildings (eleven façades).

Several of these buildings represent architectural styles from the 15th to the 19th century, including significant cultural landmarks such as Santiago's Church (1493–1545) and the Cathedral (1527–1782) (Higueras et al., 2021; Román López et al., 2022). The choice of these specific buildings is based on their architectural diversity, historical significance, and their influence on the urban microclimate of the area. The buildings were selected to capture a range of construction materials, structural layouts, sunlight exposure, and façade orientations that affect thermal behavior (Senciales-González et al., 2020).

2.2. Data collection

Data collection was characterized by the use of a custom-made bike as a mobile sensor station (Pena Acosta et al., 2022) and a handheld thermal camera as a supplementary tool (Table 1). The bike provided continuous air and surface temperatures throughout the entire route, while the handheld thermal camera recorded surface temperature data at specific points (building façades and pavements) along the route. Fieldwork was conducted from June 24 to July 5, 2024, with data collected twice daily at 11:00 a.m. and 11:00 p.m. (GMT + 2). These time intervals were chosen to correlate urban thermodynamic processes with sunlight duration and the mechanisms by which solar energy is absorbed and released by the urban fabric (Chen and Jeong, 2018).

A bicycle-based mobile urban data collection station was used to collect time-stamped air and surface temperature records (Fig. 3). The mobile unit was equipped with a sensor kit that included a display to monitor the data collection campaign in real time (A), a thermal camera (B), a thermologger for measuring air, surface temperatures and relative humidity (C), and a processing center running a dedicated Windows-based application (D). A measurement was recorded every second at a constant cycling speed of 8 km/h, which corresponds to a 2-m spatial resolution. The obtained data was processed and saved as a CSV file.

Additionally, a handheld thermal camera (Fluke TI400) provided thermal images that represent the surface temperatures of various elements within the built environment (Martin et al., 2022). While the mobile bicycle station followed the predefined route, the thermal camera supplemented this data by capturing surface temperatures focused on eight historic buildings (eleven façades) located along the route and the pavements situated directly in front of such buildings (Fig. 4). Notably, the temperature at the Cathedral was recorded repeatedly from four different streets, yielding more data and diverse perspectives. For each of the eleven designated scanning façades, thermal measurements were taken at three vertical levels: bottom, midpoint, and top of each facade. This multilevel data provided a vertical temperature profile for each structure, capturing the influence of height on heat retention. The different types of pavements in front of the buildings were also measured with a thermal camera to better understand heat absorption and release, which might have implications for thermal efficiency in historical areas.

2.3. Data processing

Due to the complexity of street canyons, time markers were used to correlate each measurement taken by the bike to specific points from the start to the end of each street segment. With measurements recorded every second, post-processing involved removing outliers, identified as values outside the upper and lower quantiles, to enhance data accuracy. After this quality control step, average readings for each street segment were calculated and stored in a CSV file for further analysis.

Table 1
Characteristics of the weather data collected.

Data acquisition unit	Category	Model	Data collected	Data source	Frequency
Bike	Mobile	Custom-made	Surface temperature Air temperature Relative humidity	Pavements HD 500 thermologger	Continuous (1 measurement per second)
Thermal camera	Handheld	Fluke TI400	Surface temperature	Building façades and pavements	Site-specific

Fig. 3. Schematic representation of the bicycle-based mobile urban data collection. Image adapted from [Pena Acosta et al. \(2022\)](#) and picture of the unit in the study area.

Fig. 4. Data collection using the thermal camera at the Málaga Cathedral (1527–1782) at the cath_lario point.

The thermal images and temperature measurements recorded by the camera, configured with an emissivity of 0.92 and a calibration range of $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, were initially organized into reports via the Fluke Connect® app. To ensure data reliability, measurements taken under unstable conditions—such as variable sunlight, wind, or the presence of transient shadows—were manually reviewed and excluded. This step ensured the integrity of the dataset, retaining only consistent and representative measurements for further analysis.

After the preliminary quality control, the data were exported to a spreadsheet for detailed analysis. The dataset included two main CSV files: one for building façade temperatures and another for pavement temperatures. Data entries were structured to facilitate cross-comparison, with columns detailing building ID, street ID, measurement date, time of day (day/night), and average temperature values at each vertical level.

In addition to the thermal records, site-specific pictures of the pavements were used to estimate the albedo of the materials. By extracting their colors according to the RGB (red, green and blue) model, the albedo was calculated as in Eq. (1), a formula used for physically-based rendering in computer graphics (Shinsoj, 2018). The validity of this formula was verified by comparing its results for the RGB code with values suggested in the literature. For asphalt pavements, for example, the value was 0.087, which is in the range of 0.05 to 0.10 for these surfaces if they are not exposed to high stress (García Mainieri et al., 2022) as is the case in a historical city center.

$$\text{Albedo} = \frac{(R/255)^{2.2} + (G/255)^{2.2} + (B/255)^{2.2}}{3} \quad (1)$$

2.4. Data analysis

The field data were first analyzed descriptively using their means and standard deviations to identify trends in potential differences by temperature type and variations by location and time of day. In the case of the pavement data collected with the thermal camera, this analysis was broken down according to the albedo of the surfaces involved to examine the influence of fabric color on temperature. In addition, the raw data collected in the field were examined through a correlation analysis using the Pearson's coefficient (Kirch, 2008), which enabled determining whether the different types of temperature had statistically significant relationship with each other.

The average values of the temperature data were also analyzed in terms of the factors that could contribute to the existence of an urban microclimate, including street geometry, anthropogenic heat release, fabric reflectivity, and the presence of blue-green spaces (Emmanuel, 2021). To take the effects of such factors into account, buffer areas were delineated around the measurement sites (Fig. 2). The radius of these buffer areas was determined according to the average distance between the measurement sites, which was 70 m. Table 2 lists the data used to create the spatial factors used to analyze the temperature data collected in the field using QGIS v3.34.10 (QGIS Development Team, 2023).

The first factor represented the heat output from buildings. Its influence on the collected temperature data was measured by calculating the building *sum per* buffer. This data source (CNIG, 2024) also contained information on blue-green infrastructure, while a derivative of the Urban Atlas such as the Street Tree Layer provides the delineation of tree patches larger than 500 m² and 10 m wide (Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, 2023). Given the size of the study area, the resolution of these two datasets may exclude smaller forms of vegetation or individual trees, which might be most common in a historical center such as that shown in Fig. 2. Consequently, the data used to account for vegetated areas was the tree inventory provided by the Municipality of Málaga. This was available as an online viewer so that the position of the trees was entered manually into QGIS using the same basemap as a reference. For the calculations per buffer, the number of trees was counted (ntrees).

The processing of the last data source resulted in three other factors related to street canyon effect and its trapping heat capacity (hbuild and svf) and the cooling of temperature due to shading (shade). Building height was calculated by masking the DSM with the building footprints. The svf stands for the proportion of visible sky and is determined based on two parameters: search distance and number of azimuth angles. These were set at 100 m and 16, following suggestions in previous literature (Dirksen et al., 2019). Shade was computed for the day and night because it depends on the position of the sun. For the daily recordings, the horizontal and vertical angle values were set to 93° and 45°, corresponding to the time of data collection (11:00 a.m.). Instead, to represent the situation at 11:00 p.m., where temperatures are the result of heat accumulation during the day, the angles used (259° and 53°) were those corresponding to the hottest time of the day, i.e., approximately three hours after the sun is at its zenith for the study area (5:00 p.m.). All these factors were calculated as averages per buffer area using zonal statistics.

After the spatial factors were prepared, their association with temperature data was calculated using Pearson's correlation coefficient. For this purpose, raw temperature data were averaged per buffer area because the spatial factors are static and did not change over the fieldwork period, except for shade. These correlations were determined for the entire dataset (day + night) as well as the day and night measurements. To complement this analysis, air, building, and pavement average temperatures were divided into low and high values according to their median. This enabled the application of the Wilcoxon test (Wilcoxon, 1945) to determine whether there were statistically significant differences between buffers classified as low or high-temperature zones based on the values of the spatial factors.

3. Results

3.1. Air, building, and pavement temperature data

To gain insight into the spatial variability of the temperature data, the field records were arranged according to their mean and

Table 2

Datasets required to characterize the spatial factors considered potential drivers of urban microclimates.

Data	Year	Format (resolution)	Source	Factor
National topographic database	2024	Shapefile (1/5000)	(CNIG, 2024)	Building area (abuild)
Tree inventory	2024	NA	(Área de Turismo del Ayuntamiento de Málaga, 2023)	Number of trees (ntrees)
Digital Surface Model (DSM)	2020	ASCII (2 m)	(CNIG, 2024)	Building height (hbuild) Shade (shade) Sky view factor (svf)

standard deviation (Fig. 5). Air temperature proved to be fairly constant regardless of the measurement site, while the building temperature fluctuated more, especially at medium altitudes. In particular, the buffer areas around Merced Square (merc_victoria and merc_obelisk) and the east façade of the Cathedral (cath_canon) reached the highest building temperatures. Pavement temperature data recorded by the bike also showed notable differences depending on the location, with the side façades of the Cathedral, the Málaga Museum and the Obelisk being the main hotspots.

Pavement temperatures measured with the thermal camera were represented by their albedo values according to Eq. (1). Although these individual values were higher than the average data recorded by the bike, the trend was similar and coincided at the same

Fig. 5. Means and standard deviations of bicycle air and pavement temperatures and handheld camera building and pavement temperatures.

hotspots. The influence of the albedo was most evident at the north façade of the Cathedral (cath_stmar), where the temperature was recorded on three surfaces with increasingly bright colors. The results indicated a better heat dissipation ability for white limestone, followed by grey limestone and black limestone. Although the surfaces with these colors were next to each other, their sunlight reflectivity resulted in appreciable temperature differences, especially during the day (nearly 7 °C). This trend was also observed in the part of Victoria Street near Merced Square (merc_victoria) but was not as evident in other cases where colors were outside the grayscale.

The association between different types of temperatures and relative humidity is depicted in Fig. 6, which shows the correlation matrices determined from the raw data collected. The results indicate that the strength of the relationships increased at night, where the correlation coefficients were higher than during the day. The coefficients of tair with tbuild_low, tbuild_mid, tbuild_high and tpave_cam increased from 0.322, 0.292, 0.380, 0.206 and 0.314 to 0.660, 0.459, 0.581 and 0.287, respectively, while those of tpave_cam with tbuild_low, tbuild_mid, tbuild_high varied from 0.201, 0.211 and -0.190 (not significant) to 0.530, 0.388 and 0.533, respectively. Instead, although tpave_bike showed good agreement with tpave_cam (0.548 and 0.558) and tair_bike (0.308 and 0.315) overall and during the day, their correlation dropped to 0.208 and 0.042 (not significant) at night. Furthermore, tpave_bike was negatively correlated with building temperatures, although these associations were very weak and not statistically significant, except for the relationship with tbuild_mid at night, whose coefficient was -0.355.

In general, the highest coefficients were found for building temperatures, with the correlation between tbuild_mid and build_high reaching the highest absolute value (0.760) at night. When comparing temperature groups, tair showed a similar degree of association with tbuild at any altitude as the different building temperatures did with each other. Instead, the coefficients achieved for pavement temperatures and either tair or tbuild were notably lower. All temperatures were negatively correlated with relative humidity, although the strength of these correlations was much lower for tair (-0.917 on average).

Although most types of temperature were positively correlated, their magnitudes almost always differed significantly. Fig. 7 shows the boxplots corresponding to the six types of temperature considered. Daily temperatures were found to be significantly higher than nighttime temperatures. In addition, all types of temperatures were statistically significant different from each other except for the following cases:

- Day + Night: tpave_bike vs tair_bike (0.05 level), tbuild_cam.low vs tbuild_cam.mid (0.10 level) and tbuild_cam.mid vs tbuild_cam.high (0.10 level).
- Day: tpave_bike vs tair_bike (0.10 level), tpave_bike vs tbuild_cam.high (0.10 level), tbuild_cam.low vs tbuild_cam.mid (0.10 level).
- Night: tpave_bike vs tbuild_cam.mid (0.05 level), tpave_bike vs tbuild_cam.high (0.05 level) and tbuild_cam.mid vs tbuild_cam.high (0.10 level).

3.2. Association between temperature data and spatial factors

The characterization of the proposed spatial variables stemmed from the maps presented in Fig. 8. The presence of buildings was high in almost all buffers, with the Málaga Cathedral standing out in terms of height. The distribution of trees was higher in the southern and northern parts of the study area, with a large concentration in the north around the Obelisk.

The aspect of the remaining variables was consistent, since the parts of the study area where the proportion of visible sky was the highest, i.e., where the building roofs were located, coincided with sunny areas according to the shade maps. The streets between buildings were the areas where sky visibility was more obstructed. The shading of these areas varied depending on the position of the sun so that they faced west during the day and vice versa at night.

The association between the spatial variables in Fig. 8 and the temperature field data was determined through the correlation matrices shown in Fig. 9. When taking averages of the entire dataset (Day + Night), shade was the variable with the highest values of

Fig. 6. Correlation matrices between weather data collected in the field.

Fig. 7. Boxplots showing the distribution of values of air, building, and pavement temperatures.

Fig. 8. Spatial distribution of the urban factors considered as potential drivers of urban microclimates (a) Buildings (b) Urban trees (c) Building height (d) Sky View Factor (e) Daytime shade (f) Nighttime shade.

Pearson’s r in relation to all temperatures (0.663 with t_{air} , 0.587 with t_{build_low} , 0.452 with t_{build_mid} , 0.384 with t_{build_high} and 0.366 with t_{pave_cam}) except t_{pave_bike} , where the coefficient fell to 0.109. Other than that, n_{trees} and a_{build} were the only other variables that showed statistically significant correlations (0.351 and -0.162) with temperature data (t_{pave_bike}).

There were only three significant correlations involving temperature variables for the daily data: t_{build_low} with $shade$ (0.324) and, again, t_{pave_bike} with n_{trees} and a_{build} (0.350 and -0.141). In addition, the negative correlation (-0.680) between t_{pave_cam} and t_{build_high} is worth highlighting. Although this relationship was negative when using the raw data (Fig. 6), it only became statistically significant when the temperature values were averaged. The results obtained for the night yielded the following significant associations: t_{air} with svf (0.746), $shade$ (0.666) and h_{build} (-0.707), t_{build_low} with n_{trees} (-0.514), t_{build_mid} with svf (-0.564) and t_{pave_bike} with svf (0.329), n_{trees} (0.485) and a_{build} (-0.260).

Aside from the temperature variables, Fig. 9 shows a number of statistically significant correlations between the spatial variables, the logic of which validated their use. These included associations between svf and $shade$ (positive: high values of svf mean fewer obstructions to sky visibility, which coincides with sunny areas), a_{build} and svf (negative: the larger the built-up area, the less “freedom” to see the sky) or n_{trees} vs a_{build} (negative: in areas with low building density there is more space for trees), to name a few.

Splitting the temperature data into low and high values based on their median revealed several statistically significant differences between both groups when analyzed in terms of some spatial variables (Fig. 10). $Shade$ was the most present spatial variable and its trend with respect to the temperatures was always the same, regardless of the time of the day: low temperatures coincided with the more shaded areas. Instead, low relative humidity levels resulted in more shade (day + night). For other spatial variables, the situation varied depending on the type of temperature and time of day. For instance, many trees meant lower building temperatures (low) at night, but higher pavement temperatures when considering the entire dataset (bike) and the daily records (camera). This also applied to the svf , whose values were proportional to the air temperatures during the night, but inverse to pavement temperatures (camera) during the day. The observed relationship between pavement temperature (bike) and building area (Fig. 9) was only significant in this case when the entire dataset was used, suggesting higher temperatures when built-up density was reduced.

4. Discussion

4.1. What are the relationships between air, building and pavement temperatures? (RQ1)

The literature contains numerous examples where air and remotely-sensed LST are analyzed. In this sense, our results showed stronger correlations between air and LST (pavement) temperatures at night, which is consistent with the findings of previous related studies (Adão et al., 2023; Goldblatt et al., 2021; Shiflett et al., 2017). It has been argued that this is related to the greater diurnal variability of LST due to the effect of solar radiation, making the differences larger in summer and early afternoon (Scolio et al., 2024). Our results are in line with this idea, as in some cases pavement temperatures were more than 13 °C higher than air temperature. These highest differences corresponded to the side entrances of the mal_musem , $cath_stmar$ and $merc_obelisk$, where the shadow effect was reduced due to the orientation of the measurement sites and/or the low presence of regular buildings, reducing the moderating thermal potential of deep building canyons (Naserikia et al., 2023).

The relationship between air temperature and building façade temperature has been less studied in the literature. The results of Abrahamsson and Thai (2021) showed that temperatures on brick façades rose significantly compared to air temperature when exposed to sunlight, but followed a similar trend without the influence of the sun. This was also the general trend in our results, with air temperature and building temperatures showing significantly better agreement at night. During the day, the differences were more frequent with increasing façade height, and coincided with the northernmost orientation of the Cathedral, which involves less solar radiation due to the azimuth angle of the sun in the North Hemisphere (González-González et al., 2022). The fact that the building

Fig. 9. Correlation matrices between the averages of weather data collected in the field and the spatial urban factors delineated in a GIS.

Fig. 10. Boxplots showing the distribution of low and high temperature values across the urban spatial factors. Only statistically significant results at the 0.10 level are presented.

temperatures were often higher than the pavement temperatures measured by bike, but not as much as the thermal camera's specific pavement temperature measurements, highlights how climate can vary within a few meters in urban environments. Consistent with previous studies (Ahmad and Eisma, 2023; Yang et al., 2021), this could be due to heterogeneity in the properties of the materials and the geometry of the streets.

The observed differences in temperature between building façades and pavements further highlight the complexity of urban microclimates. While building façades often retained higher temperatures than pavements measured by bike, thermal camera readings showed that specific pavement areas could exceed façade temperatures, particularly in locations with unobstructed exposure to solar radiation. This variability within short distances aligns with findings from previous studies (Nugroho et al., 2022), and likely stems from material heterogeneity and street geometry, both of which influence heat retention and dissipation.

The generalized presence of statistically significant differences in the magnitude of air, pavement and building façade temperatures stresses the need to consider more than one metric to properly characterize urban warming phenomena (Naserikia et al., 2023). This is particularly important for studies that focus exclusively on LST, which has become a democratic and popular option for modeling urban thermal environments due to the availability of remotely sensed data (Cheval et al., 2024). In addition, the urban factors related to the morphology and land cover of cities can have differential impacts on different types of temperature (Hong and Heo, 2023), so considering more than one metric is therefore necessary to identify the main drivers of urban microclimate (RQ3). A similar trend was observed with daytime and nighttime temperatures, which exhibited significant differences and distinct relationships with spatial factors. These variations required separate analyses to provide a comprehensive understanding of urban warming (Amorim et al., 2021).

4.2. How sensitive are the trends in urban microclimate to the weather conditions of the study area? (RQ2)

A comparison of our results with previous research in Málaga and other Andalusian cities such as Granada and Seville reveals that the central urban areas of these Mediterranean cities are characterized by dense construction materials, impermeable streets, and limited urban vegetation (shaped by both climate and limited availability of public spaces), which contributes to elevated temperatures and a pronounced UHI effect (Jadraque Gago et al., 2020; Jiménez Ferrer et al., 2019; Román López et al., 2021). While temperature differences of 1 to 3 °C were found in the central streets of Granada (Jiménez Ferrer et al., 2019), in the center of Málaga these variations were of 3 to 4 °C (Román López et al., 2021). In Málaga, the presence of sea breezes and their interaction with street orientation can significantly influence the temperature and thermal comfort in the city center during the summer months (Román López et al., 2021).

Regarding comparisons with other Mediterranean climates, studies conducted in cities such as Florence, Italy (Cureau et al., 2024)

and Athens, Greece (Founda and Santamouris, 2017) have highlighted similar challenges in terms of heat retention within densely built urban centers. In Málaga, as in these Mediterranean cities, the scarcity of open spaces limits the ability to dissipate heat (Chun and Guldmann, 2014). For example, research in Florence emphasizes how historical urban layouts and traditional building materials contribute to maintaining higher temperatures during the summer months (Cureau et al., 2024).

The differences become more pronounced when comparing the results with studies from continental climates (Hwang et al., 2014; Lee et al., 2018; Zhao et al., 2024), where the lack of moderating effects of large water bodies often leads to greater temperature fluctuations between day and night, amplifying the impact of heat waves during summer. Unlike the more stable thermal patterns in Málaga, where the Mediterranean Sea helps moderate temperatures, there are stronger thermal gradients in continental regions like Shihezi, China (Zhao et al., 2024). These differences can significantly influence urban design strategies for mitigating heat, highlighting the need for tailored approaches.

In contrast, cities with oceanic climates, such as Coventry, UK, exhibit distinct thermal dynamics. Studies in Coventry have emphasized the role of green infrastructure in reducing temperatures in school environments and urban centers during heatwaves (Namazi et al., 2024). The cooling effect of tree shade was particularly notable, reducing air temperatures by up to 6.4 °C. However, unlike Málaga, where the solar reflectivity from building façades is critical, Coventry's temperate and humid conditions reduce the effectiveness of high-albedo materials.

These comparisons highlight the need for climate-specific adaptation strategies. For instance, while reflective materials and high-albedo surfaces have proven to be effective in reducing surface temperatures in continental and desert climates (Elhinnawy, 2004), their impact in humid Mediterranean regions like Málaga is more limited due to higher moisture levels and the presence of tropical nights. Additionally, the findings suggest that strategies such as increasing urban vegetation and using permeable pavements are generally beneficial but must be adapted to the specific spatial constraints and cultural context of each region. For example, while expanding tree cover is a key recommendation for improving the thermal comfort of historical centers, the frequent space constraints in these environments may require innovative solutions such as vertical greenery and green walls to achieve similar cooling benefits.

4.3. Can the collected field records be used to identify the main drivers of urban microclimate? (RQ3)

The results of the spatial statistical analysis of the field data revealed significant evidence of the influence of several factors on the urban microclimate. In particular, they allowed the identification of shade and the number of trees as the factors most strongly related to historical center temperatures. When it comes to shade, its relationship with temperatures was positive in all cases (air, pavement and building), which is logical because the highest values of this factor refer to the sunniest areas. Since this variable came from a DSM, its effect can be attributed to any element whose height is above the terrain. Given that the study area is the historical center of Málaga, shadows are mainly created by buildings. The architecture in some buffer areas is rather dense and compact, resulting in narrow streets shaded by the presence of buildings. This argument was put forward by authors such as Gourfi et al. (2022) or Dai et al. (2019) for surface UHI, so our study shows that this effect can also apply to air and façade temperatures. Some measurement sites such as mal_museum, cath_stmar and merc_obelisk are more open, so trees could play a role in shaping the shade in their buffer areas. However, their cooling effect is also attributed to evapotranspiration mechanisms (Park et al., 2021), which may make it difficult to isolate their shading potential.

In fact, the specific variable used here to represent the influence of trees (ntrees) produced diverse results. More trees resulted in lower façade temperatures at night but higher pavement temperatures during the day. Despite trees usually close their stomata in the absence of sunlight (Zheng et al., 2021), their evapotranspiration cooling effect can still be substantial at night in hot cities (Meili et al., 2021), which is the case of Málaga. Furthermore, the greatest tree presence in our study area coincides with buffers where the svf is high, a scenario that facilitates the release of trees' cooling potential and can lead to accumulated effects (Tan et al., 2016) that could persist at night. The negative relationship between trees and pavement temperature does not agree with what has been reported in the literature. Trees lead to noticeable reductions in surface temperature during the day not only due to evapotranspiration (Gunawardena et al., 2017) but also thanks to their aforementioned shading effect (Coutts et al., 2016). A recent work by Du et al. (2024), who assessed the cooling efficiency of urban trees in 392 European clusters, concluded that the magnitude of such efficiency is amplified when using remotely sensed surface temperature records. This could explain why our results are not on the same page, as they come from measurements at specific locations or transects, differing notably from the continuous spatial distribution and usual resolution of satellite data, which can hardly be finer than 30 m. The positive sign of this relationship may lie in the fact that higher tree abundance brings with it a lack of denser built-up architecture and associated shade in the buffers where specific measurements of pavement temperature were higher, which in turn might be very localized as to be influenced by transpiration processes. In support of this argument, a significant and inverse association was found between building area and pavement temperature, suggesting that shade provided by buildings has a greater influence than tree cooling during the day.

4.4. Limitations of the study

The results derived from this study are subject to a few limitations. The first one is related to its upscaling, which might be hindered because it depends on collecting field data with different devices, which involves cost and time investments. Otherwise, the methods and equipment are described in sufficient detail that the approach taken here can be reproduced elsewhere. Another limitation in this sense is the geographical narrowness of the field campaign developed here, which refers to the historical center of a single city with specific climate and urban morphological characteristics. Replicating the process under different climate conditions and urban environments would increase the impact and validity of the results.

The research relies exclusively on field data, which can be more realistic than remotely sensed data, but have less spatial continuity. This in turn affects the spatial analysis conducted, the results of which might be limited due to the spatial specificity of the temperature data collected, making it difficult to place them in the wider context of the surrounding urban areas. Comparing the agreement between field-collected pavement temperature records and satellite observations could provide insight into the compatibility of both data acquisition techniques.

The delimitation of the data collection route is a controversial aspect of the investigation. To characterize a historical center, it makes sense to focus on a limited area; however, this limits the representativeness of the monitored zones, which could be more diverse and include more conflicting transects in terms of street geometry or presence of vegetation. The characterization of the latter was also limited because its evapotranspiration potential was only indirectly considered via relative humidity records and the analysis of number of trees per buffer area. By using a weather station to collect field data at vegetated locations, direct measurement of evapotranspiration and thus better characterization of the cooling potential of trees and other forms of vegetation would be possible. Incorporating a colorimeter into the equipment used would further refine the determination of the influence of surface solar reflectance on temperature.

The times of day for data collection were also reduced to two instants: morning and evening. Including additional measurement times in the afternoon could be an improvement as these would coincide with the peak of solar radiation and/or the hottest hour. This could be extrapolated to the season for the field campaign, since monitoring other months with more temperate conditions would add value for the climate characterization of historical urban centers.

5. Conclusions

The outcomes of this study demonstrate the importance of considering different temperature types to characterize an urban microclimate. Measurements from a custom-made bicycle station and a handheld thermal camera showed that while air, pavement and building façade temperatures in the historical center of Málaga (Spain) were generally positively correlated to each other, there were significant differences in their values. This means that research to model microclimate and warming phenomena in cities such as the UHI effect should not rely only on either surface or air temperature but draw upon both for the sake of accuracy. Furthermore, surface temperature is generally associated exclusively with land, while our results prove that façade temperatures are also substantially different and deserve specific consideration.

This also affects the analysis of temperature data from the perspective of urban factors related to the morphology and skin of cities, as the influence of such variables was found to vary when related to air and surface temperatures. Shade was the only factor that consistently had a positive cooling effect in every scenario, while the influence of trees varied depending on the time of day and temperature. Regarding pavement temperature, building density and street canyon formation were found to contribute more to the attenuation of the microclimate than vegetation shading and transpiration cooling mechanisms. The findings of this research can be used to implement thermal control solutions in historical urban centers, which are challenging to manage due to their compact layout and the presence of unmodifiable historical buildings and routes. These actions are crucial for urban adaptation in a climate change context, where rising urban temperatures pose an increasing threat. Based on the results, these solutions might consist of the distribution of awnings in strategic locations to promote shading in areas where other options are not feasible. Additionally, planting vegetation could be a promising nature-based solution, particularly in the form of green façades, given the spatial constraints of historical centers; however, a more detailed assessment of their cooling effect in such environments would be beneficial. To support this, the addition of a weather station as a third measuring device is recommended to gain insights into the influence of evapotranspiration on temperature. Implementing these strategies could not only improve thermal comfort for residents and tourists but also contribute to the preservation and resilience of historical urban areas.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Daniel Jato-Espino: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Francisco Tomatis:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Giulia Forestieri:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Monica Pena Acosta:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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